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Detection and Elimination of Outliers Using Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average Models for Annual Rainfall Data in India

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Abstract

One of the first important step in informed data analysis is detection of outliers. Even the case where the final values are considered to be often incorrect. Calculations where they can provide very important information in some times also. So it is very important to detect them before modeling and analysis, they are much smaller or much larger than the majority observations. In this paper we take annual rainfall data in India from 1985 to 2020 for detecting and eliminate outliers using different ARIMA models. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) criterion is used for selecting the best model for detect and eliminate the outliers. Different ARIMA models are empirically tested for annual rainfall data in India to detect outliers by using minimum RMSE.

Keywords: Outliers, Annual Rainfall data, ARIMA models, RMSE.

1. Introduction

One of the most common problems in any statistical analysis is the existence of some unexpected observations. Such observations may not be a part of the phenomenon under study and are known as outliers. An outlier is an observation that lies an abnormal distance from other values in a random sample from a population. In a sense, an analyst to decide what will be considered abnormal. Before abnormal observations can be singled out, it is necessary to characterize normal observations. Two activities are essential for characterizing a set of data.

(1). Examination of the overall shape of the graphed data for important features, including symmetry and departures from assumptions.

(2). Examination of the data for unusual observations that are far removed from the mass of the data.

These points are often referred to as outliers. A point beyond an inner fence on either side is considered a mild outlier. A point beyond an outer fence is considered an extreme outlier. Outlier can occur by chance in any distribution, but they often indicate either measurement error or a heavy-tailed distribution. A frequent cause of outliers is a mixture of two distributions, which may be two distinct sub-populations, or may indicate 'correct trail' versus 'measurement error', this is modeled by mixture model. Outlier points can therefore indicate faulty data, erroneous procedures or area where a certain theory might not be valid. However, in large samples a small number of outliers are to be expected.

In statistical data there are three categories of outliers, such as

1. GLOBAL OUTLIERS: a data point is considered a global outlier if its value is far outside the entirety of the data set in which it is found.
2. CONDITIONAL or CONTEXTUAL OUTLIERS: a data point is considered a conditional outlier if its value significantly deviates from the rest of the data points in the some context.
3. COLLECTIVE OUTLIERS: a subset of data points within a data set is considered anomalous if those values as a collection deviate significantly from the entire data set. But the values of the individual data points are not themselves anomalous in their contextual or global sense.

ARIMA (Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average) is widely used statistical model for time series forecasting. It predicts future values based on past values and it is highly effective for data that exhibits trends or non stationarity.

ARIMA combines three key elements denoted as (p,d,q)

AR (Auto regression, p): uses the dependent relationship between a current observations and a set of past observations.

I (Integrated, d): uses differencing to make a time series stationary.

MA (Moving Average, q): uses the dependency between an observation and residual errors from the past predictions.

When to use ARIMA: ARIMA is used for univariate data when it is deal to forecast a single variable over time and it is also used for non seasonal patterns on data with trends but without repeating seasonal cycles.

2. Related Work

Detection of outliers is how much important in research and the author focuses on the problem of detection of outliers in data streams [1]. Amulya [2] gives some of the existing outlier detection technique for the data scientists while building a machine learning model. The mixed regressive-spatial autoregressive model is used when the outliers are influential in spatial models was explained by Libin Jin et al. in [3] and also said univariate, multivariate normal sample, and linear regression model are giving better results in the detection of outliers. The Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average model is a sophisticated statistical framework that synthesizes autoregressive components, moving average processes, and differencing techniques to analyze and forecast non-stationary time series data [4].

How the Outliers arise due to changes in system behavior, fraudulent behavior, human error, and instrument error or simply through natural deviations in populations was explained by Christophe Leys et al. in [5]. Outliers have been studied in a variety of domains including Big Data, High dimensional data, uncertain data, Time Series data, Biological data etc. the Big Data is used in Health care industry. An algorithm was developed for the detection of outliers in cluster based healthcare data by Christy. A. et al [6].

Dania et al [7] explains in their work, evaluate the effectiveness of two range – based statistics, the standardized range w and the relative range k . For outlier detection among 4 common distributions with different sample sizes. Various techniques are used to detect potential outliers and reviewed by dividing the techniques into two classes, one is univariate data and the other one is multivariate data [8]. In [9], they reviewed methods of determining outliers and propose general principles for how to proceed.

Frank E. Grubb was given a procedure in 2012 for determining statistical outliers in [11]. Wada provides a survey on the important methods addressing outliers while producing official statistics when outliers are unavoidable in survey statistics [12]. In 2000, Sridhar Ramaswamy et al. had developed a high efficient partition-based algorithm for mining outliers in [13]. This process typically requires evaluating stationarity through tests like the Augmented Dickey-Fuller before utilizing autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation functions to determine the model's precise order.

Le et al. explains a survey on outlier explanations in a meaningful way from anomalous data and also explains some techniques how they address the challenges [14]. In [15], Clustering is the reliable method for detecting outliers and the type of outlier can affect performance and also an important impact on growth pattern detection and the authors believes their suggested methods can have practical applications for children growth analysis studies. Moradi explains in his paper, the problem of clustering a collection of unlabeled data points over whelming many outliers [16]. In [17], outlier analysis has been studied for several decades for the sake of data cleaning, fraud detection. However it is more possible to estimate the correct value rather than discard because later it reduces the number of degrees of freedom.

Nonparametric, deterministic, linear programming (LP) based frontier models (referred to as Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA)) have been widely used to detect the outliers with low probability was explained by Paul W. Wilson in [19]. [20], explains in machine learning how the impact of outliers.

Duraj focuses on the problem of outlier detection in data streams. A performance comparison of selected statistical algorithms like ARIMA, Exponential Smoothing State Space Model (ETS), Seasonal Hybrid Extreme Studentized Deviation (SHESD), Non Parametric Methodology and Chen-Liu Method (CHL) [24].

Box plot and multiple linear Regression method is suggest for detecting outliers in multivariate data [26]. They introduce neighborhood model as a uniform framework to understand and implement neighborhood outlier detection and also outlier detection algorithm is also given. It compares other methods like DLS, KNN and RNN. Tao suggests NPOS makes the first attempt to employ a non-parametric outlier synthesis for neighborhood detection and can be formally interpreted as a rejection sampling frame work [27].

3. Methodology

In general, Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Models are in the following form.

ARIMA (p,d,q):

p is the number of autoregressive terms,

d is the number of non seasonal differences needed for stationarity, and

q is the number of lagged forecast errors in the prediction equation.

The procedure for finding RMSE values using different ARIMA models by removing outliers using SPSS software are as follows

Step1. Switch on the computer and Select the SPSS software.

Step2. After Selecting the SPSS software, data sheet appears and enter the data and also enter variable names as year and rainfall.

Step3. Select Analyze option in the tool bar. In that there are several options, select Forecasting and we have several sub options. In that we select create models.

Step4. Select Method option, we select ARIMA and select Criteria, we give p, d, q values and click on continue.

Step5. In previous window, we have the option Statistics, click on that option, we have several options like Stationary R square, R square, Root Mean Square Error(RMSE), etc. we click on RMSE, and press ok.

Step6. We had an output of ARIMA model with a box of model statistics.

Step7. After noting the RMSE value, we remove the highest outlier, and repeat the above procedure from step3

Step8. This procedure can be repeated up to all the outliers are removed.

4. Empirical Investigation

The annual rainfall data in India from 1985 to 2020 were taken for outliers. For this data, we choose highest outliers, calculate different ARIMA models for the data and check the RMSE values.

Figure 1, The Graph of given data

Case 1. The highest outlier is 1400.6 for the year 1995, it was removed from the data and find out RMSE values for different ARIMA models with $p = 1, 2, 3, 4$, $d = 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $q = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$.

After eliminating the first outlier 1400.6 for the year 1990, the graph for the remaining data is as follows.

Figure 2, The Graph of After Eliminate First Outlier

Case 2 Remove the next highest outlier 1351.0 for the year 1993 from the data and calculate the different ARIMA models for the data.

After eliminating the two outliers 1400.6 for the year 1995 and 1351.0 for the year 1993 the graph for the remaining data is as follows.

Figure 3, The Graph of After Eliminate Two Outliers

The least RMSE values for different ARIMA models, which are almost equal when compared with case1 are shown in table 1.

Table 1, The RMSE Values

ARIMA Model	RMSE values	
	Case 1	Case 2
(4, 2, 3)	112.457	112.381
(4, 2, 4)	111.907	110.817

The RMSE value is high, so we go for next case.

Case3: Remove the next highest outlier 1331.5 for the year 1988.

After eliminating the three outliers 1400.6 for the year 1995, 1351.0 for the year 1993 and 1331.5 for the year 1988 the graph for the remaining data is as follows.

Figure 4, The Graph of After Eliminating Three Outliers

Calculate the different ARIMA models and find RMSE values. These RMSE values are compared with the case 2. The minimum RMSE values are not equal in case 2 and case 3, so we go for the next case.

Case 4. Remove the next highest outlier 1295.6 for the year 2004.

After eliminating the four outliers 1400.6 for the year 1995, 1351.0 for the year 1993 and 1331.5 for the year 1988 and 1295.6 for the year 2004 the graph for the remaining data is as follows.

Figure 5, The Graph of After Eliminating Four Outliers

Calculate the different ARIMA models and find RMSE values. These RMSE values are compared with the case 3. The minimum RMSE values for different ARIMA models, which are almost equal when compared with case 3 and as shown in table 2.

Table 2, the RMSE Values

ARIMA Model	RMSE values	
	Case 3	Case 4
(1, 2, 3)	98.277	99.511
(1, 2, 4)	100.020	99.918
(2, 2, 4)	99.639	100.180
(4, 2, 5)	102.962	102.724

The RMSE values are also high, so we go for the next case.

Case 5. We remove the next highest outliers 1243.6, 1243.5 for the years 2000, 2003 respectively.

After eliminating the six outliers 1400.6 for the year 1995, 1351.0 for the year 1993, 1331.5 for the year 1988, 1295.6 for the year 1999, 1243.6 for the year 2000 and 1243.5 for the year 2003 the graph for the remaining data is as follows

Figure 6, The Graph of After Eliminating Six Outliers

Calculate the ARIMA models for the data and find the RMSE values. These RMSE values are compared with the case 4, and the least RMSE values for different ARIMA models which are almost equal when compared to case 4 as shown in table 3.

Table 3, The RMSE values

ARIMA Model	RMSE values	
	Case 4	Case 5
(3,2,1)	96.062	95.605
(2,2,3)	95.874	94.378
(1,2,4)	100.891	100.314
(4,2,4)	95.897	95.797

Here also the RMSE values are high. So we go for the next case.

Case 6. We remove the next highest outliers 1232.5 for the year 2010 Calculate the different ARIMA models for the data and find the RMSE values. These RMSE values are compared with the case 5, and the least RMSE values for different ARIMA models which are almost equal when compared to case 5 as shown in table 4.

Table 4, The RMSE values

ARIMA Model	RMSE values	
	Case 5	Case 6
(2, 2, 1)	93.252	93.209
(3, 2, 1)	95.530	95.108
(1, 2, 2)	95.314	95.511
(3, 2, 5)	91.706	90.584

The least RMSE value is 90.584 for the ARIMA model (3, 2, 5).

After eliminating the seven outliers 1400.6 for the year 1995, 1351.0 for the year 1993, 1331.5 for the year 1988, 1295.6 for the year 1999, 1243.6 for the year 2000 and 1243.5 for the year 2003 the graph for the remaining data is as follows

Figure 7, The Graph of After Eliminating Seven Outliers

4. Summary and Conclusions

In this paper, the annual rain fall data in India were taken from 1985 to 2020, 36 years. In this data, the highest values are removed one by one and then calculated different ARIMA models for the data. Here we take the outliers for the annual rainfall data in India from 1985 to 2020 are 1400.6, 1351.0, 1331.5, 1295.6, 1243.6, 1243.5 and 1232.5. The minimum RMSE value for the data after removing the first outlier 1400.6 for the year 1995 is 110.153 for the ARIMA model (2, 2, 4).

After removing the second outlier 1351.0 for the year 1992, the RMSE values are compared to the previous case, the minimum RMSE values for different ARIMA models are given in the following table.

ARIMA model	RMSE values	
	Case 1	Case 2
(4, 2, 3)	117.754	117.183
(4, 2, 4)	116.097	115.718

After removing the third outlier 1331.5 for the year 1988, the RMSE values for different ARIMA models are compared with the previous case. There is no minimum RMSE values are equal in case 2 and case 3. So we remove the next outlier 1295.6 for the year 1999.

After remove the next highest outlier 1295.6 for the year 1999. The different ARIMA models having different RMSE values. These RMSE values are compared with the previous case. The minimum RMSE values for different ARIMA models, which are almost equal when compared with case 3.

We remove the next highest outliers 1243.6, 1243.5 for the years 2000, 2003 respectively. The ARIMA models for the data had different RMSE values. These RMSE values are compared with the previous case, and the least RMSE values for different ARIMA models, which are almost equal when compared to the previous case.

We remove the next highest outliers 1232.5 for the year 2010. The RMSE values are calculated for different ARIMA models for the data. These RMSE values are compared with the previous case, and the least RMSE values for different ARIMA models, which are almost equal when compared to previous case.

After removing seven outliers, the almost equal and least RMSE value to the ARIMA model (3, 2, 5) is 90.584 for the given data.

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